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Review Article

**NAUSEA AND VOMITING CAUSED BY CHEMOTHERAPY IN
PATIENTS WITH BREAST CANCER- A REVIEW****Fateme parooei, Sara Zamanpour and Morteza Salarzaei**Medical student, Student Research Committee, Zabol University of Medical Sciences,
Zabol, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: According to published statistics by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular diseases throughout the world. The American Cancer Society announced in its latest report that out of every eight women, one is diagnosed with breast cancer.

Methods: In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify Nausea and Vomiting Caused by Chemotherapy in Patients with Breast Cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study the Nausea and Vomiting Caused by Chemotherapy in Patients with Breast Cancer were selected.

Results: Chemotherapy alongside radiotherapy and surgery is one of the oldest and most commonly used methods for treating breast cancer. Chemotherapy is employing anti-neoplast agents attempting to destroy tumor cells by interfering with cellular functions and their reproduction.

Discussion and conclusion: Since nausea is a mental symptom, the patient himself is the best person who could provide the health team with precious and precise information about the presence and severity of the symptoms.

Key words: Nausea, Chemotherapy, Breast Cancer

Corresponding author:**Morteza Salarzaei,**

Medical student,

Student Research Committee,

Zabol University of Medical Sciences,

Zabol, Iran

Email: mr.mortezasalar@gmail.com

Tell : +989120644917

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

According to published statistics by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular diseases throughout the world. The American Cancer Society announced in its latest report that out of every eight women, one is diagnosed with breast cancer [1]. The rate of cancer in developed countries is increasing from 1 to 0.2% and in developing countries about 0.5% annually. According to a report by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer in Iran was reported to be 12% widespread and was recognized as the third most common cause of death [2]. Gastric cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer are the three common cancers in Iran respectively. Breast cancer is the first place cancer widespread among women [3]. The average age of breast cancer diagnosis in the Western countries is 56 years and in Iran 45 years. New developments in the patients care with breast cancer have increased the overall survival rate of the patients in recent years. This increase in survival has doubled the importance of predictive factors of local recurrence and distant metastases of the disease [4]. In addition, it should be noted that the progression or regression of some diseases are not constant over time, as in the stages of recovery or worsening of the disease, the occurrence of some consequences changes the course of the disease, and the disease progress declines and this risk begins to decrease in the 2-5 years after treatment, which make the recovery process speed [5].

METHODS:

In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify Nausea and Vomiting Caused by Chemotherapy in Patients with Breast Cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study the Nausea and Vomiting Caused by Chemotherapy in Patients with Breast Cancer were selected.

FINDINGS:

Chemotherapy alongside radiotherapy and surgery is one of the oldest and most commonly used methods for treating breast cancer. Chemotherapy is employing anti-neoplast agents attempting to destroy tumor cells by interfering with cellular functions and their reproduction [6]. This treatment, due to its systematic nature, causes various complications, including diarrhea, low blood pressure, drowsiness, extrapyramidal symptoms, constipation, nausea and vomiting. Among these complications, nausea and vomiting are the most common, worst and

troublesome ones experienced by 70-80% of patients, which therefore, the success of this method of treatment has largely been criticized [7]. Recent studies have demonstrated that about 70% of patients undergoing chemotherapy, even with extensive use of anti-nausea and anti-vomiting medicines still continue to experience predicted acute and delayed nausea and vomiting [8]. Predicted nausea and vomiting is a phase which the patient experiences before receiving any chemotherapy drugs. The acute type immediately appears from the time the drug is received up to 24 hours later and the delayed type shows up after 24 hours.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

Since nausea is a mental symptom, the patient himself is the best person who could provide the health team with precious and precise information about the presence and severity of the symptoms [9]. Therefore, since Likert spectrums, and especially the visual analogue, are applicable in the elderly and children, they could be proper tools for assessing the severity of nausea. The INVR is a tool, which in addition to assessing nausea, could also be applied for the case of vomiting and even gagging [dry vomiting] [10]. Interventions in which the effect of inculcation is probable on the results, it is advisable to consider the placebo group as well in addition to the control group. The significance of the placebo group in determining the inculcation effect cannot be ignored [11]. In these cases, an intervention similar to the actual one is performed to determine whether patients are psychologically reacting to the intervention in a positive manner or not.

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